

eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) and Associated Potential Limitations in the Healthcare Sector

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ABSTRACT

The black box nature of state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms almost imposed the question whether Artificial Intelligence (AI) decisions must be made transparent und humanly understandable, particularly in critical scenarios such as healthcare. This work aims to provide the audience with inspiration and starting points regarding potential limitations of XAI techniques in the context of medical decision making, especially on the local model level. The key idea is that current XAI libraries are not suitable to fully explain and justify medical diagnosis on the individual case. This is demonstrated via the example of pneumonia detection through a CCN trained on x-ray images.

KEY WORDS

Explainable ai, artificial, intelligence, xai, black box, limitations, risks, healthcare, pneumonia, detection

1 INTRODUCTION

Especially within the past decade AI has found its way more and more into the sensible application area of healthcare [1, 2, 3]. With this ever-growing level of adoption, combined with the unintuitive and intransparent nature of most machine learning models (black-box models), the need for retracing and understanding afore mentioned algorithms becomes clear. Doctors as well as researchers and lawmakers demand for eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) models [4, 5].

There are various, rather high-level definitions of what XAI is or is supposed to do, neither of them fully consistent nor identical. However, as highlighted by Tonekaboni [6] most clinical personnel “viewed explainability as a means of justifying their clinical decision-making” [7].

The latter perception, namely that XAI is a tool for explaining and justifying decision making on the individual level, might be a misunderstanding or a wrong expectation in what current XAI

tools are capable of. As stated by Ghassemi and colleagues current AI techniques are particularly useful when it comes to explaining the global model perspective but lack the ability to provide exhaustive explanation on the local level. (The global model perspective can be referred to as how the black box model in general works - including all observations, decisions, predictions, classifications etc. - from a high-level perspective, whereas the local perspective describes the individual observation, decision, prediction, or classification [7].) Hence, Ghassemi argues further that “In practice, explanations can be extremely useful when applied to global AI processes, such as model development, knowledge discovery, and audit, but they are rarely informative with respect to individual decisions.” [7]

Therefore, it is indispensable that stakeholders (or at least users) of XAI are aware of the advantages and disadvantages, as well as the limitations of XAI in its current stage of development [7].

2 CURRENT STAGE OF XAI DEVELOPMENT

When it comes to the approach of making machine learning decisions understandable and transparent for humans, there are basically two categories: models that are interpretable by design and post-hoc explainability [8].

An example for the first category is a linear regression, where the relationship between input and output variable is - obviously dependent on the audience - intuitively understandable. This relationship (strength and direction) is expressed through the coefficient. E.g.: How much changes the size of a mouse (output value) given an increase of 1 unit of mouse weight on average (input value) [9].

On the opposite side, there is the second category of models, which are applied to numerous modern machine learning challenges. These models are complex, and their input data is often high-dimensional, what makes an intuitive understanding difficult, if not impossible. Examples for the second category are models that process e.g., unstructured data such as image, sound or text data [10]. In these cases, the focus is more on trying to explain the models process of decision making post-hoc, which means, after the decision has been made. One common approach to do so are heat-maps (or saliency-maps) [11]. The latter colorize those regions in an, for instance, x-ray image, which contributed to an algorithm’s decision. Although this approach is intuitively understandable (and widely used also in the healthcare sector) at the first glance, it simultaneously outlines the existing limitations of such XAI techniques [12].

The output x-ray image on the right visualizes those regions of an x-ray which contributed to a pneumonia diagnosis through an AI model. The pervasive limitation or even danger is that the illustrated region does not only contain information/ symptoms that clearly stand for pneumonia, but also contain inconspicuous regions in the context of pneumonia detection. Consequently, a human doctor cannot finally evaluate whether the model appropriately discovered the disease due to the actual symptoms within the red area of the x-ray image, or if other shapes or non-human factors such as pixel values were responsible for the AI diagnosis (although it is correct in this case) [13]. One could argue that the final interpretation still belongs to the human healthcare expert. The described situation, in combination with the famous

cognitive error called confirmation bias, might lead to the following assumption in the case of the pneumonia example: The rough region makes sense from a medical point of view, so humans tend to consider the model’s decision as correct. But this can be a very misleading and dangerous assumption from the local model perspective. Other explainability methods (e.g., SHAP/ LIME) tend to have comparable behaviours [14], the description of which would exceed the scope of this work.

Figure 1 – XAI applied to CNN for pneumonia detection

3 ARE POST-HOC EXPLANATIONS STILL HELPFUL?

Selbst and Borcas [15] answer that question with a “yes, but” stakeholders need to be aware of the limitations. Current explainability methods offer an insight into the model to a certain degree, but they rarely clarify whether and individual model

decision itself was correct or not. To put it in other words: For the end user, who tries to understand an individual model decision, it is more important and helpful to know why a model was looking at a particular section, rather than knowing where the model was looking. Even more concise: XAI makes things seemingly crystal-clear - even from the local model perspective - but they aren't.

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the authors perspective there is no doubt, that XAI will have an ever-growing impact in the healthcare sector and will have great benefit on patient safety. However, its intuitive appeal might provoke over-hasty and simplified justifications – especially on the local level – and foster biases when it comes to model evaluations.

On the other hand, the current explainability methods are powerful tools to verify model's decisions on the global model perspective, for developers and auditors.

As already mentioned within this work – as long as there are no substantial developments when it comes to explaining local model decisions without input of human domain knowledge experts – user of such XAI methods need to be aware of the limitations. Further research in this field will hopefully one day reduce mentioned limitations.

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